

Building the Data-driven Archive

Scaling-up and automation with ETL and asynchronous event-driven messaging architecture

Problem: Linear process, every service transforms data

Proposal: Centralised, automated, data infrastructure

First: Non-linear data flow

- Data transformations are centralised, audited, and repeatable.
- Archivists configure data pipelines via a GUI without needing to code.

- New records are available to all downstream services at the same time.
- Services load data when they are ready.

Now: Event-driven orchestration

- Message flows initiate work and signal task completion.
- Activities are discrete and asynchronous.
- Message database enables reporting.

Next: Central data, new data services

- Add workflows to handle a greater variety of records.
- Central store for digital objects and metadata.

- New suite of shared data services.
- Deprecate old workflows gradually.

Further iteration: Data catalogue for machine-readable insight into content & flows

Future direction: Data governance for re-usable business rules & logic